

Gene therapy may benefit inherited ichthyoses with concurrent fungal infections and severe ichthyoidoses

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Abstract- Despite the fact that inherited ichthyoses with simultaneous fungal infections have been documented for more than 50 years, the connection between the two remains unknown. Because ichthyosis makes it harder to identify a concurrent fungal infection, it's important to pay close attention to prevent missing or delaying a diagnosis. The underlying ichthyosis makes treating fungal infections more difficult, and severe and recurrent infections need further attention. Those with severe ichthyoses may benefit from gene therapy in order to avoid fungal infection. More clinical and laboratory research is needed, however, to fully comprehend the mechanisms of action and provide a foundation of knowledge from which innovative therapy alternatives might be created.

I. INTRODUCTION

Ichthyoses are a set of genetic keratinization illnesses characterized by dry skin, scaling, and hyperkeratosis, which are frequently coupled with erythroderma and fissures. They are classified as nonsyndromic or syndromic, with several subtypes linked with mutations in various causal genes in both (1). Although cutaneous fungal infections are relatively uncommon, people with ichthyoses appear to have a higher risk of getting them (2, 3). A typical consequence of the syndromic ichthyosis known as keratitis, ichthyosis, and deafness (KID) syndrome is chronic fungal infection (4).

II. FUNGAL INFECTIONS AND NON-SYNDROMIC ICHTHYOSSES

Learn about the history of fungi and the many forms of fungi.

Trichophyton (*T.*) *rubrum* was initially identified as the causal pathogen for lamellar ichthyosis with fungal infection in 1972 (8). Since then, other subtypes of ichthyoses have been discovered, along with various forms of fungus. In two babies with RXLI and IV, Kamalam et al. described tinea glabra and tinea manuum and unguium (onychomycosis) linked with *T. rubrum* (9), whereas CIE with *T. rubrum* was also often reported (3, 10–12). In addition to *T. rubrum* and *T. mentagrophytes*, ichthyosis patients have been shown to have infections with *Epidermophyton* (*E.*) *floccosum*, *T. tonsurans*, *T. verrucosum*, *Geomyces pannorum*, and *Candida* (*C.*) *albicans* (6, 7, 13-16). There have also been cases of ichthyosis coupled with widespread and resistant fungal infections (3, 7, 11, 13, 17, 18). Technology advancements have expanded study into the causes of fungal infection in ichthyosis patients (19), and a link between genotype and susceptibility to fungal infection has been postulated (20). Given that > 40% of patients with such mutations had fungal infections, several researchers hypothesized that individuals with ARCI caused by mutations in SDR9C7 were prone to recurrent fungal skin infections (20, 21). In four additional investigations, however, none of the eight patients with ichthyosis caused by SDR9C7 mutations had fungal infections (22-25). In individuals with ARCI caused by SDR9C7 mutations, the overall risk of fungal infections may be similar to that of individuals with ARCI produced by other genes (22-25). However, these studies only looked at a few cases, and further research is needed to back up the findings. *T. rubrum* was the most common causal pathogen of superficial dermatophytosis in patients with ichthyosis, followed by *T. mentagrophytes* and *E. floccosum*, according to the reported cases, which is consistent with the spectrum of fungal infections in the general population (2, 3, 9–14, 17, 26).

Clinical signs and symptoms

The symptoms of underlying fungal infections differ depending on the ichthyosis subtype. Dry skin, scaling, itching, palmar hyperlinearity, and keratosis pilaris are minor symptoms in IV patients, which are relieved in the summer. Atopic dermatitis (AD) is frequently associated with ichthyosis vulgaris (27).

Large, black, polygonal scales on the neck, extensor surfaces of the limbs, and trunk are common in RXLI patients, giving them an unclean appearance. LI, like ARCI, has severe symptoms such as huge, plate-like scales, palmoplantar hyperkeratosis, and severe ectropion but only mild erythema, whereas CIE has fine, white scaling with varied degrees of erythema. Harlequin ichthyosis is the most severe kind of ichthyosis, characterized by thick, horny, armor-like plaques that cover the whole body surface, as well as severe eclabium and ectropion (1).

Some ARCI patients were collodion infants at birth, with skin that produced big, brown scales when the membrane was shed, a clinical presentation observed predominantly in LI and HI patients (28). Patients with ichthyoses may have nail dysplasia as well.

Tinea capitis, corporis, manuum, and unguium are frequent manifestations of fungi that cause ichthyoses (3, 9, 11). Tinea capitis causes moderate non-inflammatory alopecia with or without scaling, as well as a pustular eruption on the scalp with abscess development. Tinea corporis often manifests as circular plaques with a ring of erythema around the edges, often accompanied by scaling in the center region. When the fungus invades the dermis and subcutaneous tissues, superimposed bullous Majocchi's granuloma might appear as pink to red perifollicular papules, pustules, or nodules, in contrast to superficial dermatophytoses. Dry, scaly, and erythematous skin on the hands are symptoms of Tinea manuum. Distal subungual onychomycosis, white superficial onychomycosis, proximal subungual onychomycosis, and Candida onychomycosis are four kinds of onychomycosis that cause extensive nail-bed hyperkeratosis and nail disintegration. *T. rubrum*-induced onychomycosis begins with a yellowish discoloration and develops proximally as a streak, eventually affecting the whole nail, which becomes brittle and separates from the bed (2).

Ichthyosiform symptoms often appear in early childhood or shortly after birth, with accompanying fungal infections appearing months or years later (5, 13, 14, 26). Alopecia, papules, pustules, and worsening of scaling in the summer may indicate fungal infections (5, 9). Tinea corporis, for example, might show as a broad eruption of erythematous annular plaques with superimposed bullous Majocchi's granuloma (12, 13, 17). However, ARCI can readily disguise scaling, palmoplantar keratosis, and erythematous changes in the early stages (29). Patients with IV and AD identified in childhood had an itchy rash on the trunk and limbs, as well as strongly infiltrated nummular erythematous plaques with peripheral scaling, which were readily mistaken for AD, despite the fact that the symptoms were caused by *Trichophyton* (14, 26).

Nail abnormalities are caused by both ichthyoses and onychomycoses, and while differential diagnosis is critical in clinical practice, it can be confounding. In ichthyosis, nail dysplasia is always symmetrical, affecting many or all nails, and presenting as hyperkeratosis and hypertrophy with homogenous high density (30). Onychomycosis, on the other hand, is frequently asymmetrical and affects one or more nails, with the four typical forms indicated above serving as indicators. Onychomycosis is indicated by new-onset discolored, brittle nails and complete nail loss. Furthermore, potentially lethal sepsis caused by *Candida*, particularly *C. albicans* and *C. tropicalis*, has been observed in collodion newborns with ARCI, primarily LI and HI (15, 16).

One patient with RXLI was infected with *T. verrucosum*, which caused ichthyotic scaling to clear up in well-defined regions in the afflicted regions. After the fungal infection was cleared, the scaling returned quickly, indicating that fungal compounds, such as enzymes involved in lipid metabolism, might be useful in the treatment of RXLI (6). Finally, the symptoms of fungal infections are unusual and might be mistaken for ichthyoses, leading to a delay in diagnosis.

III. SUSCEPTIBILITY MECHANISMS

Patients with ichthyosis are more susceptible to fungal infections, while the exact reason is unknown. Disruption of epidermal barrier function, poor cell-mediated immunity, and delayed keratin scaling have all been shown to enhance the risk (3, 26). Recent research has suggested certain molecular and cellular pathways.

IV. DEFICIENCY IN THE SKIN'S BARRIER FUNCTION:

The two outermost skin layers, the stratum granulosum (SG) and stratum corneum (SC), are deficient in most ichthyoses, leading to impaired skin barrier function. For terminal differentiation, there must be abundant production and modification of particular lipids and proteins, and the lipids must subsequently be delivered to the SC. Exocytosis delivers vital chemicals such as free fatty acids (FFAs), cholesterol, and glucosylceramides (precursor of -hydroxy-acylceramide (-HAC)) to the SC matrix, which consists of an extensively cross-linked lipid-protein matrix with strong extracellular lamellar bilayers. Together with tight junctions, corneodesmosomes, and intercellular connections, this matrix provides a strong skin barrier. Filaggrin also binds to keratin and has a role in skin barrier function (28, 31). Finally, antimicrobial peptides (AMPs) are delivered by LB to the SC intercellular domains (32). The natural skin barrier offers mechanical resistance to microbial agents, and the somewhat acidic environment inhibits fungus development, while FFAs in the SC also hinder fungal development.

Various forms of ichthyoses have different causal genes, resulting in diverse paths of damage to the skin barrier. FLG mutations linked to IV impair the structure and function of filaggrin, resulting in cytoskeletal abnormalities such as aberrant LB loading and lamellar bilayer disruption. Furthermore, filaggrin metabolites known as natural moisturizing factors (NMFs), which are important for SC hydration, are diminished. Reduced NMFs enhance transepidermal water loss and skin surface enlargement, making the skin more susceptible to fungal invasion (33-35). Deletions in STS linked to RXLI cause a buildup of cholesterol sulfate in the skin, resulting in a failure of the liquid-crystalline transition, keratinocyte retention, and SC thickening (36). Mutations in several genes, including TGM1, ABCA12, CYP4F22, ALOXE3/ALOX12B, NIPAL4, and SDR9C7, may cause ARCI (28, 37). The majority of these genes are involved in an essential metabolic pathway for the production of -HAC, which binds to the cornified lipid envelope and aids in the formation of the skin barrier. Abnormalities in LB formation, loading, and exocytosis, according to Chan et al., increased the likelihood of fungal infection (19).

The release of glucosylceramides to nascent LBs is disrupted by ABCA12 mutations, resulting in a lack of lipid and other LB cargos in the SC

interstices, such as antimicrobial peptides (AMPs). By altering membrane permeabilization, AMPs play a key function in pathogen protection (38). LBs develop properly in epidermolytic ichthyosis (EI), a keratinopathic ichthyosis caused by keratin gene mutations, but exocytosis of their contents is impeded because of cytoskeletal damage produced by keratin abnormalities. In individuals with HI, levels of LB-derived proteins such as AMP cathelicidin (LL-37) and human-defensin 2 were significantly reduced (19, 32). Normal skin in the SC has an acidic pH (about 5.6), which aids cutaneous defense and prevents fungal infection (39). In individuals with ichthyosis, the pH of the skin surface and SC was much higher, which may have ramifications for the skin's self-defense capacities (40).

Overproduction of keratin and keratinophilic fungi: Patients with ichthyosis have delayed scaling, thicker SC, altered turnover, and aberrant sebaceous and sweat glands, all of which contribute to cutaneous fungal colonization by facilitating fungus adhesion and penetration (41). Keratinophilic fungi invade keratinized tissues, and ichthyotic skin produces more keratin than normal skin, making it a more suitable environment for fungal colonization (14, 26, 42). In the persistence of fungal infections, both overproduction and delayed desquamation of keratin play crucial roles (3).

Host immunological conditions: Host immunity is important in fungal infections, and anti-fungal defenses are thought to be mediated through cell-mediated immune responses (43). Individuals with ichthyosis are generally immune-competent, but diabetic or immunocompromised patients are more likely to develop generalized fungal skin infections (44). Patients with ichthyosis, on the other hand, may be atopic (26, 45). With relation to T-helper (Th) 1 and Th2 imbalances, the link between atopy and persistent fungal infection is well-known (46, 47). Immediate hypersensitivity reactions are linked to chronic, recurring infections. However, despite the fact that many patients had immediate hypersensitivity and high IgE levels, Jones found that they were not protective (48). The Th1 and Th2 profile responses linked to their ability to recover from fungal infection may differ, with the Th1 response favoring resistance and the Th2 response favoring susceptibility. Ludwig et colleagues. postulated that fungal infections might be caused by antigen-specific immunological aberrations in atopic skin (change from Th1 to Th2) (45). They linked LI to atopy, emphasizing the importance of being aware of potential links between various types of ichthyoses and atopy.

T. rubrum is the most prevalent etiologic agent of dermatophytosis, accounting for almost 80% of all cases, and is also the most often described pathogen in individuals with ichthyoses (49). *T. rubrum* generates chemicals that decrease the host immune response, such as mannan, a cell-wall glycoprotein that may inhibit the inflammatory response, particularly in atopic patients or those who are vulnerable to mannan-induced suppression of the cell-mediated immune response (44). Mannans have been shown to inhibit keratinocyte proliferation and epidermal turnover, particularly in individuals with ichthyosis (42, 46), as well as lymphocyte differentiation and mitogen-induced proliferation (50, 51). The immune activity of macrophages was lost after *T. rubrum* infection or impaired by fungal exoantigens and mannan, according to Campos et al. (52). TLR 2 was recently discovered to play a key role in *T. rubrum* phagocytosis in monocytes, and reactive oxygen species and nitric oxide suppressed *T. rubrum* growth in cell lines in vitro (49, 53). *T. rubrum* lysin M proteins may aid in the fungus' defense and allow it to evade immune monitoring (54). These discoveries have offered a possible treatment target in addition to enhancing our understanding of the etiology.

V. TREATMENT AND DIAGNOSIS

Clinical symptoms and laboratory confirmations are used to diagnose fungal infections. Because of the similarities between lesions, clinical signs vary depending on the kind of fungus and site of infection, which can be deceptive in individuals with ichthyoses. In patients with ichthyosis who present with atypical signs such as baldness, papules, pustules, worsening of scaling in the summer, and brittle or damaged nails, fungal infections should be considered and further laboratory exams performed (11). The diagnosis may be aided by microscopy, fungal culture, and histological studies. Biopsy is intrusive, therefore it's usually reserved for individuals who haven't responded to therapy (55). It's possible that a Wood's lamp examination, serum testing, and molecular diagnostics like the polymerase chain reaction will be necessary. Microscopic inspection or culture are also used to diagnose onychomycosis. KOH solution is typically used to evaluate nail clippings containing dystrophic subungual debris, but the other procedures mentioned above can also be utilized. In addition, in individuals with ichthyosis, atopy should be explored (27).

Antifungal treatment should be started as soon as a diagnosis of fungal infection is established. Topical terbinafine is the first-line treatment for local superficial infections in ichthyosis patients, such as tinea corporis, manuum, pedis, and unguium, while allylamines like butenafine and naftifine, as well as topical azoles like ketoconazole, miconazole, and clotrimazole creams, are suitable alternatives. Systemic oral antifungal medications, such as oral terbinafine or itraconazole, may be required in patients with widespread or resistant infections, while griseofulvin is also an option, but with significantly reduced effectiveness. Due to the difficulty of topical medicines penetrating and lasting in individuals with onychomycosis, oral treatment is more usually necessary (2, 18, 55). In individuals with ichthyosis, however, broad and repeated fungal infections are prevalent, with the majority of documented cases having generalized infections and up to 20% having recurring fungal infections. In individuals with ichthyosis, a combination of oral and topical antifungal medications is frequently employed. In babies with HI and severe *Candida*-related sepsis, intravenous fluconazole and amphotericin B were also utilized. Concurrent ichthyosis consequently enhances susceptibility to fungal infections while also making treatment more challenging.

Acanthotic SC and clogged sweat ducts may make it more difficult for antifungal agents to penetrate the skin (17), and an impaired skin barrier may thus provide a conducive environment for fungal colonization while also making it more difficult to eradicate the infection, making patients with ichthyosis more susceptible to recurrent fungal infections and increasing the need for systemic antifungal therapy. However, further research is needed to fully understand the processes.

Ichthyosis treatments should aim to improve skin barrier function in order to reduce the risk of fungal infection. Traditional therapies for diverse ichthyoses include emollients and topical keratolytics, whereas oral retinoids that can modulate keratin expression are advised in individuals with severe forms, notably keratinopathic ichthyosis. Vitamin D has also been shown to be effective (28, 56). Anti-inflammatory drugs, such as anti-interleukin12/23 monoclonal antibody, anti-tumor necrosis factor agents, and enzyme replacement therapy, such as topical recombinant human TGM-1 liposomes, recombinant kallikrein, and-HAC, have been shown to be effective in cell lines and animal models, and warrant further research (28, 57–60). Ex vivo gene editing also improved filament integrity in EI keratinocytes (61).

VI. FUNGAL INFECTION AND KID SYNDROME

Keratitis, ichthyosis, and deafness syndrome is a rare genodermatosis characterized by hyperkeratotic skin lesions, neurosensory hearing loss, and vascularizing keratitis (62). It is linked to mutations in the connexin 26 (Cx26) gene, GJB2. In keratinocytes, mutant Cx26 proteins cause hemi-channel malfunction and Ca²⁺ overload, resulting in lipid loading problems and skin barrier malfunction (63). Generalized verrucous hyperkeratosis and reddish-orange reticulated plaques are two skin symptoms (4). Fungal infections, particularly those caused by *Candida albicans* and afterwards *T. rubrum*, are common consequences of KID. Impaired skin barrier function and host immunological conditions comparable to nonsyndromic ichthyoses have been linked to increased vulnerability (4, 64). In response to antigens, including *Candida* antigens, normal lymphocyte profiles and proliferation have been documented (65). However, concerns have been expressed about immunological dysregulation and primary systemic immunodeficiency. In the first instance of KID with refractory cutaneous candidiasis infection, Rerknimitr et al. discovered an absence of Langerhans cells. Langerhans cells are required for the formation of Th17 cells, which are critical for *Candida* infection prevention (66). In mammals, toll-like receptors are important for innate immunity, and TLR2 and TLR4 have been linked to the immunological response to *T. rubrum* infection (67, 68). TLR2 expression was reduced in a KID patient with *T. rubrum* infection, according to Ma et al., perhaps leading to vulnerability. TLR4 was, however, unaffected when compared to the normal epidermis (69).

In the majority of patients, oral fluconazole or itraconazole was successful (4, 64, 69). Lee et al. recently reported some effectiveness of allele-specific short interfering RNA in individuals with KID syndrome (70), in addition to comparable therapies for nonsyndromic ichthyosis. Although more research on GJB2-targeted therapy is needed (70-272), it might be a game-changing treatment for KID and subsequent fungal infections.

VII. CONCLUSION

Despite the fact that hereditary ichthyoses with concomitant fungal infections have been recorded for over 50 years (8), the link between the two is still unclear. Because ichthyosis makes it difficult to detect a concomitant fungal infection, cautious attention is required to avoid a missed or delayed diagnosis. The underlying ichthyosis complicates the treatment of fungal infections, and severe and recurring infections require special attention. Gene therapy might benefit those with severe ichthyoses and avoid fungal infection. However, more clinical and laboratory research is needed to understand the mechanisms of action and offer a foundation of knowledge on which novel therapeutic options might be developed.

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